

IMPROVING THE INITIAL CLEANING OF AN UNWASHED WOOL*УДК677.027.251.3***Dadaboyev Farkhodjon Makhmudjonovich***Namangan Engineering Technological Institute**great teacher**Email: farhodjon1975@bk.ru**Tel. +998945017570***Kayumov Juramirza Abdiramatovich***Namangan Engineering Technological Institute**Doctor of Sciences**Email: j_kayumov@mail.ru**Tel. +998990510855***Annotatsiya**

Ushbu maqolada yuvilmagan mahalliy jun xomashyosini qayta ishlashda samarali usullardan foydalanish, titish-savash qurilmasini takomillashtirish hamda unda qo'llanilgan ishchi baraban va qo'zg'almas pichoqlarni ishlash va konstruksion parametrlari keltirilgan. Shu bilan birga jun xomashyosida qiyin ajraluvchi o'simlik qoldiqlaridan to'la tozalash yo'llari bo'yicha olib borilgan ilmiy tadqiqot tanijalari keltirilgan.

Аннотация

В статье описано об использовании эффективных методов обработки немытой местной шерсти, совершенствовании молотилки и параметрах используемого в ней рабочего барабана и неподвижных ножей. Вместе с тем представлены результаты научных исследований способов полного удаления трудноразделяемых растительных остатков в шерстяном сырье.

Annotation

The article describes the use of effective methods for processing unwashed local wool, improving the thresher and the parameters of the working drum and fixed

knives used in it. At the same time, the results of scientific studies of methods for the complete removal of hard-to-remove plant residues in woolen raw materials are presented.

Key words: technology, primary cleaning, working drum, fixed knife, amino acids, carbonation, bump roller, groove.

In the textile industry, which is one of the main branches of the light industry, the primary purification of raw materials is one of the main processes. The initial cleaning process is important to ensure the continuity of technological processes. Difficult to separate plant residues in wool fibers, which are one of the natural fibers, the separation of horns and thorns is one of the main problems facing manufacturers.

Wool differs fundamentally from other fibers in its chemical structure, which affects its strength, flexibility, staple properties and permeability. Wool is a protein fiber containing more than 20 amino acids [2], [3.59], [4.38].

These amino acids are protein polymers. Wool also contains small amounts of fat, calcium and sodium. These factors should be taken into account when processing wool.

The main goal of this study is to improve the design of a technological machine for cleaning sheep and goat wool in Uzbekistan and to determine its main operating parameters. Increase production capacity and contribute to the enrichment of the national economy through the creation of energy-saving devices for cleaning technological processes, effectively using available opportunities. To this end, a compact, high-performance wastewater treatment plant has been developed to replace the series of machines installed in the carbonation process in existing wool processing plants. The main goal is to improve the efficiency of production. plant using a low-energy spinning device, consisting of interchangeable parts [3.59], [7], [10.156], [13.97].

Wool fibers are mainly cleaned in two ways: mechanical and chemical. The mechanical method is carried out using fenders. The initially selected wool fibers

are manually separated from the bundles and transferred to the combing equipment using a feeder. The whipping machines, which consist of 2 or 3 drum piles, help to partially separate the bundle of fibers that are too intertwined with each other and separate organic and mineral waste in them. Partially refined wool fibers are transferred to washing machines. Difficult to separate plant residues in the wool remain untreated. This type of waste management costs a lot of money. Chemical processing uses carbonic acid to remove plant debris by incineration in a multi-boiler plant. The advantages of this method are the complete removal of plant residues in the wool fiber, while the disadvantages are factors such as the length of the aggregate, excessive labor, excessive energy consumption, excessive consumption of space and excessive consumption of water, as well as human health. There are also significant side effects, as well as cases of exacerbation of allergic diseases [1.136], [8.152], [9.260].

Cleaning unwashed wool with a snare drum is designed to separate semi-coarse and coarse fleece wool from dirt. With this method of cleaning wool, the high natural properties of the wool are preserved. The essence of this process consists in dragging the wool of wool under the fixed knife, pressed against this drum, by the surface of the rotating working drum, and the subsequent removal of contamination at the edge of the fixed knife by the striker. To implement this process, it is necessary that the coefficient of friction of the pair "fiber-surface of the working drum" was higher than the coefficient of friction of the pair "fiber-steel knife".

Structurally, a device for realizing the cleaning process with a working drum can be performed in different ways, depending on the design of the fender. Fenders can be made on the basis of the use of a reciprocating or rotary motion. In cleaning unwashed wool, we take it into the research with a rotting fender and this will sharply increase the productivity of machines and cleaning wool [3.59], [5.21], [7], [11.42].

There are fenders with soft and hard rebound.

The fender with a soft rebound contains a shaft, a flexible amortizator with a knife attached at the end, made of thin sheet hard steel. Amartizers with impact knives are attached to the shaft by means of bolts and strips. In the section for cleaning wool, the striker is installed close to the working roller, made of technical leather discs or artificial substitutes. A fixed knife is pressed against this roller via a leaf spring. The gap between the fixed knife and the impact roller is 0.5-1 mm.

The process of cleaning wool is as follows. The unwashed wool, half-scuffed on the peg drums, is fed in a uniform flow to a rotating work roller, which captures the wool fibers and drags them under the fixed knife, while pulling the seed and various contaminants to the edge of the knife.

The pulling force P , under the action of which the woolen fiber is pulled under the fixed knife, is determined by the formula

$$P = T_1 - T_2 = F(\mu_1 - \mu_2)$$

where T_1, T_2 is the friction force of the wool fiber, respectively, about the working roller and the fixed knife;

$$T_1 = \mu_1 F, \quad T_2 = \mu_2 F;$$

F is the force of pressing the fixed knife to the working roller;

μ_1, μ_2 - coefficients of friction of pairs “fiber-working roller” and “fiber-fixed knife” [1.136], [6.352], [9.260].

Under the action of the pulling force, some of the fibers can be detached from dirt, but the bulk of the woolen fibers are separated when struck by rotating knives. On the knife, the part of the wool fibers that had sufficient tension is usually torn off. The rest is torn off in portions over many with a blow knife as the woolen fibers are pulled under the fixed knife. The separated plant residues, which have lost contact with the working roller, fall out into the mesh opening and a general battery screw seed conveyor rolls down the chute, and the fiber is fed through a vacuum valve to a pneumatic transport system.

The described soft-rebound fender is essentially an inertial action organ, i.e. The rebound of plant residues by such a rapidly rotating organ is accomplished due to

the kinetic energy of the rotating masses of the hammer knives [13.97],[14] [15.138].

A significant disadvantage of the soft rebound fender is the low durability of the shock absorbers and insufficient force when the knife strikes the plant residues, which is noticeable when reworking some new varieties of hexa fibers, characterized by increased fiber attachment strength to plant residues. At the same time, it is impossible to increase the impact force by increasing the speed of rotation of the fender, since this causes the transition of wool fibers to waste.

In contrast to the described one, the rigid fender is made in the form of a cylinder, on the surface of which steel impact knives are rigidly fixed. The speed of rotation of the hard-type rebound organ is approximately 3 times less than the speed of the soft rebound organ.

The work roller has a shaft, keys, working discs and clamping washers with nuts. The work roller surface is highly wear resistant and has a high friction coefficient of 0 fiber and low 0 fixed knife.

For a long time, working discs were made of walrus, buffalo or seal skin. Recently, in connection with the search for new, cheaper and highly efficient artificial materials, the industry uses discs from various substitutes on rubber-cord, paper and other bases.

When assembling the working rolls from new disks, the assembled package is upset on a press before tightening with nuts with a pressure applied in the range of 7.0-8.0 N / mm² [1.136], [8.152], [9.260].

After assembling the working rollers, they are grinded on top and screw grooves are cut on this surface with a pitch of 800-1000 mm, a depth of 5 mm and a width of 3 mm. The distance between the grooves is 20-25 mm. The presence of grooves on the surface increases the gripping power of the roller and eliminates the possibility of accumulation of plant residues and wool fibers at the working edge of the knife.

During operation, as they wear, the working rollers are resharpened to a smaller size.

Research by the Central Research Institute of Chemical Industry has established that the diameter of the roller and the rotation speed significantly affect productivity. With an increase in the diameter of the roller and its speed, the productivity increases. The optimum rotation speed of the roller is 2-3m / s. With an increase in the speed of rotation above 3 m / s, excessive heating of the surface of the roller occurs and its damage [6.352], [8.152], [9.260].

In conclusion, it can be said that the cleaning of the unwashed wool in the snare drum and the stripping knife cleaning system are more efficient. As a result of research, an improved version of the new wool spinning device can be used. The proposed improved device provides greater economic efficiency when used in wool cleaning enterprises. It also increases the productivity of the wool mill. The main thing is to be able to completely process local wool and supply it to the textile industry [13.97].

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